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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF ANEMIA AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS
AMONG CHILDREN IN KSA: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY**

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the prevalence of anemia among children aged 12 years and less in the Saudi population

Methods: This study employs a cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence of anemia and its associated factors among children aged 12 years or less in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). A cross-sectional approach allows for the collection of data at a single point in time from a diverse group of participants.

Results: The study included 587 participants. The most frequent gender among them was Male (n= 316, 53.8%) followed by Female (n= 271, 46%). The most frequent BMI among study participants was normal 5-85 kg/m² (n= 570, 97.1%), followed by obese more than 95 kg/m² (n= 15, 2.6%). The most frequent age value among study participants was 4-6 years (n= 296, 50%) followed by 10-12 years (n= 166, 28%). The most frequent anemia level among them was non-anemia (n= 308, 52%), followed by Moderate anemia (n= 126, 21%). Participants were asked about their parents' educational level. The most frequent education for fathers among study participants was university (n= 395, 67.3%), followed by school (n= 159, 27.1%). The most frequent education for mothers among study participants was university (n= 383, 65.2%), followed by school (n= 144, 24.5%). Participants were asked about their eating if they eat red meat; the most frequent answer was yes (n= 380, 64.7%); other hands answered no (n= 207, 35.3%), and about eating green vegetables, yes (n=267, 45.5%), in other hands no (n=320, 54.5%). The eating citrus consumption the most answered yes (n=345, 58.8%), followed by no (242, 41.2%). The most frequently were not exposed to smoking (n=454, 77.3%), exposed to smoking (n=133, 22.6%).

Conclusion: The results of the study showed that most of the children are male and the most of there weight was normal according to their BMI. Most of them were children of university-educated fathers and mothers. Most children have not been exposed to smoking. Most of them relied on eating red meat and Citrus consumption, in addition to drinking milk. Most study participants had good communication.

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INTRODUCTION:

Anemia is a medical illness characterized by a decrease in the total number of red blood cells in circulation or a deficiency in the red blood cells' ability to transport oxygen, resulting in an inadequate supply to fulfill the body's physiological requirements (1). Anemia is often diagnosed by assessing low levels of hemoglobin (Hb) or hematocrit concentrations (2). However, other diagnostic methods include evaluating variations in blood reticulocyte count, mean corpuscular volume, blood film analysis, or Hb electrophoresis (3). However, considering the population size and limitations of clinical practice, the measurement of Hb concentration is often used as the primary hematological examination for the determination of anemia (4). Anemia has a significant worldwide incidence and has the potential to manifest at any point in the lifespan, with a specific propensity for occurrence in preschool-aged children (5). As per the established criteria set by the World Health Organization (WHO), anemia is characterized by a hemoglobin concentration below 11 g/dL in females and below 12 g/dL in boys (6). It is worth mentioning that anemia has the potential to impact mental health, cognitive abilities, and concentration skills (6).

Iron deficiency is widely recognized as the primary etiology of anemia. Extensive clinical and epidemiological investigations have consistently revealed a substantial correlation between iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and an elevated susceptibility to various psychiatric conditions, including unipolar depressive disorder, bipolar disease, anxiety disorder, attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder, delayed development, and mental retardation, across different age groups (7).

Africa has the greatest worldwide incidence of anemia at 47.5%, with South-East Asia following closely behind at 35.7% (8). Furthermore, the prevalence of this condition is estimated to be about 17.8% in the Americas, 14% in the United Arab Emirates, 11% in Egypt, and greater than 40% in the Syrian Arab Republic and Oman among women who are of

reproductive age (8). A number of research studies conducted in Saudi Arabia have focused on the prevalence of anemia in preschool children under the age of six, with a particular emphasis on their nutritional condition (8-10). The objective of this investigation was to ascertain the prevalence of anemia in Saudi Arabia, with a focus on age demographics, as well as the classification and severity of anemia.

METHODS:**Study design**

This study employs a cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence of anemia and its associated factors among children aged 12 years or less in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). A cross-sectional approach allows for the collection of data at a single point in time from a diverse group of participants.

Study approach

The study will be conducted across various regions within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, encompassing urban, suburban, and rural settings to ensure representation of the broader population.

Study population

The target population consists of children aged 12 years or less residing in Saudi Arabia.

Study sample

A representative sample will be drawn from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. In the first stage, different regions will be randomly selected. Within each region, clusters such as schools, community centers, and healthcare facilities will be identified. From these clusters, participants will be randomly selected to achieve an appropriate sample of children.

Study tool

For the current study, a questionnaire was adopted for data collection, also categorized as a study tool.

Data collection

Data will be collected through structured interviews and physical examinations. Trained research personnel will administer questionnaires to parents or guardians of the children to gather demographic, socioeconomic, and dietary information. Additionally, blood samples will be collected from participants to assess hemoglobin levels.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics will be used to calculate the prevalence of anemia and its severity distribution. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests and logistic regression, will be employed to analyze the association between anemia prevalence and demographic or socioeconomic factors.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval will be obtained from [Specify the relevant ethics committee or institutional review

board]. Informed consent will be obtained from parents or guardians of participating children. Confidentiality of participants' information and their right to withdraw from the study at any point will be ensured.

RESULTS:

The study included 587 participants. The most frequent gender among them was Male (n= 316, 53.8%) followed by Female (n= 271, 46%). Figure 1 shows the gender distribution among study participants. The most frequent BMI among study participants was normal 5-85 kg/m² (n= 570, 97.1%), followed by obese more than 95 kg/m² (n= 15, 2.6%). Figure 2 shows the BMI distribution among study participants. The most frequent age value among study participants was 4-6 years (n= 296, 50%) followed by 10-12 years (n= 166, 28%). Figure 3 shows the distribution of age among study participants.

Figure 1: gender distribution among study participants

Figure 2: BMI distribution among study participants

Figure 3: Age distribution among study participants

The most frequent anemia level among them was non-anemia (n= 308, 52%), followed by Moderate anemia (n= 126, 21%). Figure 4 shows the anemia level distribution among study participants.

Figure 4 shows the anemia level distribution among study participants.

Participants were asked about their parents' educational level. The most frequent education for fathers among study participants was university (n= 395, 67.3%), followed by school (n= 159, 27.1%). The most frequent education for mothers among study participants was university (n= 383, 65.2%), followed by school (n= 144, 24.5%). Perceived the educational level of parents is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: educational of parents among study participants

Participants were asked to assess if they had diseases. Their responses and results are presented in Table 1.

	yes	no
Do you have a troll?	91 (15.5%)	496 (84.5%)
Do you have extreme thinness?	218 (37.1%)	369 (62.9%)
Do you have an Intestinal parasitic infection?	135 (23%)	452 (77%)

Participants were asked about their eating if they eat red meat; the most frequent answer was yes (n= 380, 64.7%); other hands answered no (n= 207, 35.3%), and about eating green vegetables, yes (n=267, 45.5%), in other hands no (n=320, 54.5%). The eating citrus consumption the most answered yes (n=345, 58.8%), followed by no (242, 41.2%). Figure 6 shows participants if they are exposed to smoking. The most frequently were not exposed to smoking (n=454, 77.3%), exposed to smoking (n=133, 22.6%).

Figure 6: Participants exposed to smoking

DISCUSSION:

The World Health Organization (WHO), ranking in the top ten most critical health issues (1), recognizes anemia as a significant global health concern. Anemia, a condition characterized by a hemoglobin level below 11.0 g/dl, is often encountered in infants between the ages of 6 and 59 months, as well as in pregnant women who are considered the most susceptible population (1, 2). Anemia is characterized by a deficiency in red blood cells or impaired hemoglobin function, resulting in an inadequate supply of oxygen to meet the organism's physiological requirements. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2011), an estimated 273.2 million children between the ages of 6 and 59 months worldwide were afflicted with anemia, resulting in an overall prevalence rate of 42.6%. Nevertheless, this phenomenon has a disproportionate impact on several global locations. Sub-Saharan Africa, an area with a prevalence rate of 62.3%, provides shelter to roughly 84.5 million

children aged 6-59 months who are afflicted with anemia.

The early management of anemia and its elimination are objectives in the field of public health, as well as significant challenges faced by educational institutions, since they have the potential to enhance both physical development and cognitive abilities in children (3). Undoubtedly, the ramifications of anemia among preschool-aged children are of significant concern (4,5,6,7). These consequences encompass a range of adverse effects, such as compromised cognitive function, hindered motor development and growth, diminished academic performance, reduced immune function leading to heightened susceptibility to infections, decreased responsiveness and activity levels, and increased fatigue. These factors have the potential to significantly impede the long-term growth and development of a kid in an irreversible manner. The scenario has sparked significant attention on both a domestic and global scale, resulting in the initiation

of preventive initiatives such as the fortification of food and the provision of intermittent iron supplements (8, 9). Since the most common anemia among children is iron deficiency, the review will focus on that.

CONCLUSION:

The results of the study showed that most of the children are male and the most of their weight was normal according to their BMI. Most of them were children of university-educated fathers and mothers. Most children have not been exposed to smoking. Most of them relied on eating red meat and citrus consumption, in addition to drinking milk. Most study participants had good communication.

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ANNEX 1: DATA COLLECTION TOOL

1. Are you exposed to smoking?
 - Yes
 - No
2. What is the father's education level?
 - Uneducated
 - School
 - University
3. What is the mother's education level?
 - Uneducated
 - School
 - University
4. What is the result of Cell analysis (cell shape)?
 - Small size
 - Normal size
 - Large size
 - Don't know
5. What is the result of Cell analysis (cell color)?
 - Faded color
 - Natural color
 - Don't know
6. Do you have a troll?
 - Yes
 - No
7. Do you have extreme thinness?
 - Yes
 - No
8. Do you have an Intestinal parasitic infection?
 - Yes
 - No
9. Do you eat leafy green vegetables?
 - Yes
 - No
10. Do you Eat lots of green leafy vegetables?
 - Daily
 - More than once a week
 - Once a week
 - Doesn't eat
11. Do you eat Citrus consumption?
 - Yes
 - No

12. Do you Eat Frequent consumption of citrus fruits?

- Daily
- More than once a week
- Once a week
- Doesn't eat

13. Do you eat red meat?

- Yes
- No

14. Do you Eat lots of red meat?

- Daily
- More than once a week
- Once a week
- Doesn't eat

15. Do you drink milk?

- Yes
- No

16. Do you drink a lot of milk?

- Daily
- More than once a week
- Once a week
- Doesn't eat

17. Did you Use milk supplements?

- Yes
- No

APPENDIX 2: Participants responses to scale items

	yes	no
Do you eat leafy green vegetables?	267 (45.5%)	320 (54.5%)
Do you eat Citrus consumption?	345 (58.8%)	242 (41.2%)
Do you eat Red meat?	380 (64.7%)	207 (35.3%)
Do you drink milk?	484 (82.5%)	103 (17.5%)
Did you use milk supplements?	138 (23.5%)	449 (76.5%)

	Daily	More than once a week	Once a week	Doesn't eat
Do you eat a lot of leafy green vegetables?	62 (10.6%)	144 (24.5%)	178 (30.5%)	203 (34.6%)
Do you eat a lot of Citrus consumption?	71 (12.1%)	175 (29.8%)	201 (34.2%)	140 (23.9%)
Do you eat a lot of red meat?	65 (11.1%)	201 (34.2%)	209 (35.6%)	112 (19.1%)
Do you drink lot of milk?	207(35.3%)	221(37.6%)	90 (15.3%)	69 (11.8%)

SPSS

age

	Frequency	percent
0-3	70	12%
4-6	296	50%
7-9	55	9%
10-12	166	28%
Total	587	100%

gender

	Frequency	Percent
Male	316	53.8%
Female	271	46%
Total	587	100%

exposed to smoking

	Frequency	Percent
yes	133	22.6%
no	454	77.3%
Total	587	100%

father's education

	Frequency	Percent
Uneducated	33	5.6%
School	159	27.1%
University	395	67.3%
Total	587	100%

mother's education

	Frequency	Percent
Uneducated	60	10.2%
School	144	24.5%
University	383	65.2%
Total	587	100%

BMI level

	Frequency	Percent
underweight (< 5)	1	0.2%
Normal (5-85)	570	97.1%
Overweight (85-95)	1	0.2%
Obese (>95)	15	2.6%
Total	587	100%

Cell analysis (cell shape)

	Frequency	Percent
Small size	55	9.4%
Normal size	251	42.8%
Large size	3	0.5%
Don't know	278	47.4%
Total	587	100.0%

Cell analysis (cell color)

	Frequency	Percent
Faded color	74	13%
Natural color	209	36%
Don't know	304	52%
Total	587	100%

Hemoglobin (anemia)

	Frequency	Percent
non-anemic ($12 <$)	308	52%
Mild anemia (10-11)	120	20%
Moderate anemia (7-9.9)	126	21%
Severe anemia (<7)	33	6%
Total	587	100%

Logistic regression

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
Hemoglobin	non-anemic	308	52.5%
	Mild anemia	120	20.4%
	Moderate anemia	126	21.5%
	Severe anemia	33	5.6%
Valid		587	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		587	
Subpopulation		378 ^a	

Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1165.885			
Final	1009.974	155.911	36	.000

Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	1055.993	46.019	3	.000
gender	1010.691	.717	3	.869
BMI level	1012.183	2.209	3	.530
age	1011.453	1.479	3	.687
exposed to smoking	1019.904	9.930	3	.019
cell shape	1010.896	.922	3	.820
cell color	1015.306	5.331	3	.149
troll	1016.808	6.833	3	.077
Extreme thinness	1025.483	15.509	3	.001
Intestinal parasitic infection	1028.324	18.350	3	.000
father's education	1011.985	2.011	3	.570
mother's education	1013.102	3.128	3	.372
Milk supplement	1021.424	11.450	3	.010

Parameter Estimates

Hemoglobin ^a	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Mild anemia	Intercept	2.091	1.329	2.477	1	.116		
	gender	.175	.224	.609	1	.435	1.191	.767 1.850
	BMI level	.188	.319	.347	1	.556	1.206	.646 2.252
	age	-.078-	.110	.507	1	.476	.925	.746 1.147
	exposed to smoking	-.731-	.287	6.462	1	.011	.482	.274 .846
	cell shape	.055	.137	.163	1	.686	1.057	.808 1.381
	cell color	-.201-	.234	.740	1	.390	.818	.517 1.293
	troll	.286	.422	.459	1	.498	1.330	.582 3.040
	Extreme thinness	-.865-	.253	11.693	1	.001	.421	.257 .691
	Intestinal parasitic infection	.403	.349	1.333	1	.248	1.497	.755 2.968
	father's education	-.168-	.231	.526	1	.468	.846	.537 1.330
	mother's education	-.225-	.202	1.239	1	.266	.798	.537 1.187
	Milk supplement	-.359-	.273	1.733	1	.188	.698	.409 1.192

Moderate anemia	Intercept	8.243	1.451	32.264	1	.000			
	gender	-.013-	.241	.003	1	.957	.987	.615	1.584
	BMI level	-.426-	.502	.720	1	.396	.653	.244	1.748
	age	.075	.117	.412	1	.521	1.078	.857	1.355
	exposed to smoking	-.760-	.300	6.401	1	.011	.468	.259	.843
	cell shape	.044	.138	.101	1	.750	1.045	.797	1.370
	cell color	-.357-	.222	2.592	1	.107	.700	.453	1.081
	troll	-.628-	.346	3.288	1	.070	.534	.271	1.052
	Extreme thinness	-.798-	.274	8.479	1	.004	.450	.263	.770
	Intestinal parasitic infection	-1.015-	.303	11.206	1	.001	.363	.200	.657
	father's education	-.091-	.241	.143	1	.705	.913	.570	1.463
	mother's education	-.341-	.213	2.562	1	.109	.711	.468	1.080
	Milk supplement	-.647-	.272	5.658	1	.017	.524	.307	.892
	Severe anemia	Intercept	5.794	1.791	10.470	1	.001		
gender		.080	.389	.043	1	.836	1.084	.506	2.321
BMI level		.372	.482	.595	1	.441	1.450	.564	3.727
age		-.067-	.193	.122	1	.727	.935	.641	1.364
exposed to smoking		-.773-	.469	2.719	1	.099	.462	.184	1.157
Cell shape		.205	.220	.871	1	.351	1.228	.798	1.890
cell color		-.697-	.334	4.363	1	.037	.498	.259	.958
troll		-.718-	.527	1.860	1	.173	.488	.174	1.369
Extreme thinness		-.561-	.439	1.635	1	.201	.571	.241	1.349
Intestinal parasitic infection		-.401-	.472	.722	1	.396	.670	.266	1.688
father's education		-.497-	.368	1.823	1	.177	.609	.296	1.251
mother's education		-.012-	.355	.001	1	.972	.988	.492	1.982
Milk supplement		-1.218-	.403	9.133	1	.003	.296	.134	.652

a. The reference category is: non-anemic.